

Hyperspectral imaging for identification of irregular-shaped microplastics in water

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Solving the problem: water makes spectral feature detection of microplastics difficult
- Hyperspectral image study of mixtures of ten microplastics sunken/floating in water
- A detailed experimental demonstration on how to remove the effects of water
- Spectral feature addressing table to identify, and locate microplastics in water
- Opening to future application of the method for on-site detection of microplastics

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

In this article, we demonstrate detection and identification of ten microplastic types directly in a water sample using an identification table derived from microplastic hyperspectral images. We selected a total of fourteen wavelengths which can be used to distinguish these ten microplastic types. We enhanced the visibility of these wavelengths by computationally removing water and baseline correcting with reflectance at 1550 nm. This method avoids, prevents, and eases most of the laborious sample preparation mandatory prior to analysis with robust techniques such as Raman spectroscopy and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy. The ten different plastics were studied in water, first separately and then in a mixture. The microplastic concentrations varied depending on microplastic type and were kept <12 mg/ml per type. Finally, detection and identification were confirmed pixel-wise in a hyperspectral image of a realistic water matrix simulant including mixtures of only a few microplastic particles. All measurements have been performed with microplastics of different sizes and irregular shapes made in-house by milling commercial pellets and sheets. It enabled the establishment of a procedure for the identification of these vicious particles in real water samples. The present measurement setup

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of hyperspectral imaging and method of data analysis of a mixture of microplastics directly from a water-based sample may open a path towards fast, reliable, and on-site detection.

1. Introduction

The detection of microplastics (MPs) in water is made difficult by the water itself as, due to its physical properties, it masks or suppresses the spectral fingerprints of MPs (de Vries et al., 2023; Knaeps et al., 2021). For this reason, most of the aquatic MP studies opt to extract the MPs from the water matrix before analysis. In many cases, the extraction and separation of MPs from other fragments is difficult, laborious, or not possible, and there is a need for methods and devices that can detect MPs, in-situ, emersed, and floating in water. In this study, we contribute to tackling this challenging task by creating an identification table from hyperspectral image data to detect and identify microplastics directly in water. The novelty lays in the enhancement of spectral signatures of MP types in water by removing water and baseline correcting their reflectance spectrum and using first derivative. If such a method has already been used for microplastic identification from dry or filtered samples, no prior study has reported on the direct identification in water. Furthermore, we validate pixel-by-pixel the detection and identification procedure in a hyperspectral image of a realistic water matrix including mixtures of only a few MP particles.

Current detection of microplastics is in majority based on robust optical spectroscopic methods such as Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) and Raman spectroscopies (Asamoah et al., 2021). Besides their indisputable reliability, these methods require sample pre-treatment, e.g., removal of organic materials leading to a possible misidentification of the presence of MPs. As a fact, organic materials, e.g., lignin, cellulose, have spectral fingerprints that overlap or are in close vicinity to those of MPs. Time-consuming pre-treatment and measurements of MPs requires expertise, and measurements performed in laboratory with well-controlled conditions. Alternative approaches exist. One is based on hyperspectral imaging (HSI) of plastic litter. It has been suggested as a promising useful method for the detection of plastic items in field conditions by airborne sensing (Garaba et al., 2018) and harvesting of marine plastic litter (Garaba and Dierssen, 2020). In addition, collected floating MPs from sea surface have been investigated by HSI (Serranti et al., 2018) and other rapid HSI-based methods for detection of MPs in seawater have been reported. They involve measurements after filtration of water sample using a paper filter (Shan et al., 2019), study of a sand sample (Vidal and Pasquini, 2021), and report detection of MPs size down to 100 μm (Zhu et al., 2020). The potential of HSI in the detection of MPs has been recently highlighted in the review articles by Faltynkova et al. (2021) and Huang et al. (2021). In these studies, HSI is usually performed on dry MP samples and separately for each plastic type. Here, we present a different approach by studying a mixture of different plastic types in its water environment. Such a method is suitable, for instance, for the detection and identification of possible MPs in domestic tap water, industrial wastewater, or open water environments.

Another advantage of HSI is that it has the capability to measure an area. While spectrometers (e.g., Fourier and Raman) perform point-based measurements, where the size of the measurement point depends on the construction of the device and can reach a radius of a few millimeters, hyperspectral imaging systems record spatially varying spectral information (Sharma et al., 2003). It yields a two-dimensional array of spectral measurements, which are computationally converted into a stack of images of the same scene acquired at multiple wavelengths of light, i.e., spectral channel images. This stack is a three-dimensional image cube, also called a spectral cube, with every pixel containing a spectrum and it has a defined spatial and spectral resolution. Here we use a line-based hyperspectral imaging system. This system captures spatial and spectral information one line at a time and requires the inclusion of a moving stage to record the whole scene line

by line.

2. Materials and methods

In this work, we collected and analyzed hyperspectral images of ten MP samples using a line-based spectral imaging system, consisting of two systems namely SpecimV10E (Specim, Spectral Imaging Ltd., Finland) (Specim, 2024a) and Specim N25 (Specim, Spectral Imaging Ltd., Finland) (Specim, 2024b). Section 2.1 describes the studied samples. Section 2.2 provides details on the experimental setup for HSI using a line-scan imaging system. Section 2.3 presents the image post-processing steps leading to the identification of the various MPs present in the samples.

2.1. Samples

Ten MP samples (see Table 1) are fabricated from pristine commercial plastic pellets. Polyethylene (PE) and polypropylene (PP) pellets were supplied by Borealis (Austria), polystyrene (PS) was supplied by Basf (Germany), polyamide (PA) by DuPont (USA) and polyester (PET) by Indorama (Indonesia). Polyvinyl chloride (PVC) was supplied as sheets by Goodfellow Ltd. (UK). Precut plastic pieces (in case of PVC sheets) or raw pellets are milled after dipping in liquid nitrogen. This keeps the plastics brittle and below their glass-transition temperature (T_g) for the duration of the grinding process to prevent melting deformation and filter jams (Hrovat et al., 2024; Peiponen et al., 2023). It yields irregular-shaped MPs. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) picture of an MP is shown in Fig. 1a. Different sized sieves have been used to sort the MPs by size after milling. Considering the resolution of the line scan cameras to be used in our experiment, we limited our study to relatively large microplastics using sieves of 1 mm in most of the cases. The average MP particle generated with a 1 mm sieve is roughly 250 μm in size and the size range is roughly 50–400 μm . This is due to the cryogenically cooled and therefore brittle plastics breaking during the milling process. A detailed description on the cryogenic milling protocol used to fabricate these samples is reported in Hrovat et al. (2024). Fig. 1b shows a photograph of the artificial microplastics and Table 1 summarizes the plastic types and the sieve sizes used to generate the MP particles. The ground MPs were separated into fractions using mechanical sieving. In the case of PS and HDPE, smaller sieve particles were used and in the case of PET the >200 μm fraction was used.

The samples were imaged in custom-made cuvettes that can hold water (see Fig. 1c). The cuvette is made of a microscopic glass slide (1 mm thick) and acrylic laser cut walls (8 mm-height). The circular cups have a diameter of 21 mm, and the elongated ones are 66.5×19 mm with a 9.5 mm radius at the ends. The bottom and walls are fixed together with clear silicone to avoid water leaks.

Table 1

List of the different plastic types under investigation and size of the sieve used to sort them after milling.

Plastic type	Sieve size
PS1 - polystyrene	1 mm
PP - polypropylene	1 mm
LLDPE - linear low-density polyethylene	1 mm
UPVC - unplasticized polyvinyl chloride	1 mm
MDPE - medium density polyethylene	1 mm
PET - polyethylene terephthalate	>200 μm
PS80 - polystyrene	80 μm
PVC - polyvinyl chloride	1 mm
PA - polyamide (nylon)	1 mm
HDPE - high density polyethylene	80 μm

Fig. 1. Samples and preparation of the experiment. a) Scanning electron microscopic picture of a polypropylene microplastic fabricated by milling. b) Photograph of the ten grinded microplastic samples. c) Photograph of the elongated and circular cuvettes (one microscopic glass holds three circular cuvettes) used to host the samples in water. d) Arrangement of the cuvettes and sample holders on the measurement table. Top down: one triplet of circular cuvettes holding water; first elongated cuvette with a mixture of LLDPE, MDPE, HDPE, PS1, and PS80 in water; second elongated cuvette with a mixture of PP, UPVC, PVC, PA, and PET in water; four triplets of circular cuvettes holding PET, LLDPE, MDPE, HDPE, PA, PS1, PS80, PP, UPVC, and PVC – one MP per circular cuvette.

A small amount of each MP was placed in one circular cup and filled with tap water. The elongated cups were used to hold mixtures of different MPs. The concentrations of individual MPs were ranging between approximately 5.5 mg/ml, for the MPs with smallest particles (e. g., HDPE 80), and 11 mg/ml for the MP with largest particles (PET). To simulate a realistic set of samples from industrial waters, another set of cuvettes filled with tap water were contaminated with a few particles of each MP. The samples will be referred to as ‘individual MPs’ when the concentration is so high that the MP particles aggregate together, ‘mixture of MPs’ for samples with several MP types, and ‘realistic mixture of MPs’ when the concentration of different MP types is of a few units in the cuvette. Cuvettes are filled with tap water up to 1 mm from the edge (1 ml for the circular cuvette and 4.5 ml for the elongated ones) and gently shaken to ensure a correct mixture between MPs and water. Once filled, the cuvettes were placed on the moving table covered with an absorbing black canvas enabling the scanning with the line-based systems. A cuvette containing only tap water was used as a reference. Fig. 1d shows the arrangement of the samples on the measurement moving table. All the samples are imaged within one measurement and under similar conditions, following the procedure described in the next Section 2.2.

2.2. Hyperspectral imaging procedure

Two line-based spectral imaging systems have been used to image the MP samples. Together these systems cover the electromagnetic spectrum range from 400 nm to 2500 nm. The first system is a SpecimV10E sensitive in the visible and near infrared range (VIS-NIR, 400 nm < λ < 1000 nm). The second is a SpecimN25 which measures in the short wavelength infrared range (SWIR, 1000 nm < λ < 2500 nm). It is important to note a significant variation of spatial resolution between the two devices, i.e., the VIS-NIR system counts 2144 pixel/line, while the SWIR system only 320 pixel/line. Table 2 summarizes the main features and specifications of the two line-scan systems used to perform the measurements.

Both devices are fixed onto a structure above a moving table. On both sides of the devices, a set of seven halogen lamps are placed for an illumination of the sample at an angle of 45° from the normal to the moving table. As the table moves the devices images one line at a time until all the samples are scanned. The scans are done with one device at a time. Fig. 2a shows a schematic of the imaging setup and Fig. 2b and c are pictures of the setup taken during the imaging. One can see the disposition of the cuvette on the table, the scanning direction, as well as the acquisition line orientation.

Three set of images, or scanning of the samples, were acquired. The first set images only individual MPs and mixtures of MPs without water (referred to as MPs in air). The second scan images the same individual MPs and mixtures, in high concentrations, of MPs in water (referred to as MPs in water). The third scan images realistic mixtures of MPs in water. The output of each measurement is a spectral cube. Before each scan, we capture a white and dark reference scan under the same imaging

Table 2
Summary of the two devices’ settings used in this study.

	VIS-NIR	SWIR
Device	SpecimV10E	SpecimN25
Spectral range	400–1000 nm	1000–2500 nm
Spectral resolution	5 nm	6 nm
Spatial resolution per line	2144 pixels	320 pixels
Lens type	50 mm – changeable aperture	56 mm – fixed aperture
Aperture size	5,6	na
Exposure time	55 ms	1 ms
Frame rate	18 Hz	60 Hz
Spectral binning	8	1

conditions to correct in post processing any effects that noise and illumination has on the signal. These scans are also used to obtain the reflectance from the recorded signal (flat-field correction in Section 2.3). The white reference is a scan of a uniform white sample (Spectralon®) (Labsphere, 2024) plate placed at the front of the moving table. The dark is a scan obtained by closing the shutter of the lens. For baseline correction purposes we also acquire scans of a cuvette containing only water. Section 3.1 discusses the results of these measurements.

2.3. Procedure for the identification of MPs in water using SWIR hyperspectral images

Since a procedure is established here, it is important to detail some information on various technical and computational steps to obtain reliable data on the presence of MPs. Therefore, we next describe the way hyperspectral images are post-processed in our method to identify MPs in water using hyperspectral images. To identify MPs in water using hyperspectral images, we designed a procedure including five main steps. First, the images must be post-processed to remove the effects of imaging noise, illumination, and water (Steps 1 and 2 on Fig. 3). Then, a training data set needs to be collected to perform the analysis of each MP (Step 3a). Once collected this data is analyzed to determine the spectral features (Step 4) that will be used for identification of MPs (Step 5). Fig. 3 shows a flowchart of this procedure.

An output raw spectral image contains spectral information that is a mix of noise, illumination, and the reflectance of the sample. A traditional operation used in spectral image post-processing that removes some noise, spatial non-uniformities, and the effect of the illumination from the captured signal (Yoon and Park, 2015) is called the flat-field correction. In Step 1, flat-field correction is performed on each output spectral image, forming the spectral cube, using the white and dark reference images captured under the same conditions, as follows:

$$r^i(x, y) = \frac{v^i(x, y) - v_{\text{dark}}^i(x, y)}{v_{\text{white}}^i(x, y) - v_{\text{dark}}^i(x, y)}, \quad (1)$$

where x and y are the coordinates of a pixel in an image, and v^i , v_{dark}^i , and v_{white}^i are output spectral images (for spectral channel i) of the MPs, dark reference image, and white reference image, respectively. After this operation a spectral reflectance cube is obtained. This means that each pixel location of an image contains a spectral reflectance information. This correction operation is performed on all sample cases (MPs in air, MPs in water, realistic mixture of MPs in water) using their corresponding white and dark references.

After flat-field correction the reflectance of the microplastics is still affected by the reflectance of water. This makes their identification difficult because of an overall flattening of the main spectral features. This problem has been explained in the case of microplastics study in seawater, and it is usually avoided by filtrating the samples (Shan et al., 2019). Our approach differs, since we aim at identifying MPs directly from (water + MPs)-samples without a filtration process. To reveal spectral features that could be usable for MP identification but are masked by water, we propose a two-step correction (Step 2) First, we subtract the reflectance of water from the reflectance obtained in Step 1 at every pixel location as follows:

$$r_{\text{N,water}}^i(x, y) = r^i(x, y) - r_{\text{water}}^i, \quad (2)$$

where $r^i(x, y)$ is the reflectance image (for spectral channel i) after flat-filed correction and r_{water}^i is the reflectance of water. r_{water}^i is obtained by taking an average of a 2×2 pixels area from the center of the flat-field-corrected spectral image of a cuvette containing only water. This is sufficient because the value is constant over the entire cuvette surface. Then we correct this water-subtracted image with the $i = 1550$ nm channel as follows:

Fig. 2. Experimental setup. a) Schematics of the setup. b) and c) Photographs of the experimental setup during the imaging process.

$$r_N^i(x, y) = \frac{r_{N,1550}^i(x, y) - \min(r_{N,1550}(x, y))}{\max(r_{N,1550}(x, y)) - \min(r_{N,1550}(x, y))}, \quad (3)$$

where

$$r_{N,1550}^i(x, y) = r_{N,water}^i(x, y) - r_{water}^{1550 \text{ nm}}(x, y), \quad (4)$$

$r_{N,water}^i(x, y)$ is the water-subtracted image (for spectral channel i) obtained from (2) and $r_{water}^{1550 \text{ nm}}(x, y)$ is the $i = 1550 \text{ nm}$ channel of that water-subtracted image. We chose 1550 nm as the baseline correction channel because all MP samples in water have a flat reflectance at this wavelength (see Fig. 4 black curve). The final spectral image, $r_N(x, y)$, is an image where the influence of water is removed, and the spectral features are revealed.

Next, we use the corrected image of MPs in water to collect representative spectra for each MP (step 3a). The reference spectra for

individual MP were obtained by averaging a spectral area of 2×2 pixels. This area is manually selected from the center of cuvettes containing individual MPs, i.e., one large piece of a single plastic type per cuvette. These representative reference spectra are then used in Step 4 to analyze and extract spectral features of each MP. While Step 3a prepares the individual MP spectra, Step 3b focuses on preparing the microplastic mixture images for the microplastic identification step. As the image contains a lot of information that is currently not the focus of our procedure, we decided to manually select regions of interests (ROIs) in each image and limit the investigation to those regions. The selection was done semi-manually, i.e., using a customized algorithm, creating a mask that will block out (set to value 0) all regions that are not of our interest.

Using data from Step 3, we perform spectral analysis and extraction of spectral features for each MP type (step 4). The spectrum analysis consists of a manual search for the characteristic peaks and valleys in the spectra for each MP type. Most of spectral features are not sharp or well

Fig. 3. Flowchart of the procedure showing the main processing and analysis steps. Steps 1 and 2 are spectra post-processing steps done on every image. Step 3a is representative microplastic spectra selection and 3b is spectral image region of interest selection step. Step 4 is the microplastic spectra analysis step. Step 5 is the step to detect the microplastics in the spectral images.

delimited. To ease the identification of the features enabling the MP-type discrimination, we compute the first derivative of each baseline corrected spectrum using MATLAB function $gradient(F)$. This allows us

to examine the first derivative and therefore the fluctuation of the spectra, which is a clearer indicator than the direct spectrum (see Fig. 6). The sign and the value of the first derivative suggests if a spectrum has a peak (positive) or a valley (negative) at a certain wavelength. The output for this step is a spectral feature addressing table (see Table 3) that collects the identified peaks and valleys, which are MP-type specific and can be used to identify them in a mixture.

Each pixel of each spectral image acquired by the cameras and properly corrected as explained in the previous steps are compared with the spectral feature addressing table. In case of a match, the pixel is labeled with the corresponding plastic type. Otherwise, the pixel remains considered as background or colored in black if it could be another type of material or a superposition of several MPs. To validate this step, we first tested our method on the same images from which we collected representative samples. Then we applied the method to the mixture images with higher amounts of MPs. Finally, we apply the method on realistic MP mixture images.

3. Results

In this section, we report on the analysis of MPs in water following the procedure described above. To validate our choice for the correction steps, we present first the spectral features of MPs in air and in water. Then we show the results on the enhancement of the spectral features with our method and present the key features found to be useful to identify MPs in water enabling the establishment of the spectral feature

Fig. 4. Reflectance plots in the wavelength range 400–2500 nm of the ten microplastics in their pure form (denoted by the name of the plastic) and in water (denoted by the name of the plastic and the word ‘water’). Note that around 1010 nm a step is observed due to the change from VNIR to SWIR device.

Table 3
Spectral feature addressing table used for creating a plastic identification mask.

a) Values of first derivative for each microplastic at selected wavelengths λ .

MP type	Spectral Features (nm)																				
	1130	1187	1212	1263	1421	1427	1661	1680	1698	1717	1736	1761	1768	1906	2146	2171	2241	2266	2317	2355	
HDPE	-0,03		-0,02								-0,02		-0,01							-0,08	-0,07
LLDPE			-0,04		-0,01						-0,06		-0,04							-0,07	-0,06
MDPE			-0,06		-0,02						-0,07		-0,04							-0,06	-0,05
PVC	-0,04		-0,003							-0,01	+0,01	-								-0,01	
UPVC	-0,04		+0,005							-0,01	+0,009										
PS1	-0,05		-			-		-0,06							-	-0,02				-	
			0,0003			0,005									0,09					0,002	
PS80	+0,0005		-0,004	-0,01		-		-0,04							-	-0,03				-	
						0,001									0,05					0,001	
PP	-0,06	-0,03							-0,06											-0,1	-0,05
PA	-0,05		+0,004								+0,002	-0,003	-				0,0003				
													0,002								
PET	-0,07	+0,008	+0,003		-0,01		-0,03							-0,02						-0,03	

b) Identification mask. Green indicates that a negative value of the first derivative at a pixel location for this wavelength will mark the corresponding pixel in a mask as 1 and orange will do the same for positive first derivative values. Else the value 0 will be assigned.

MP type	Spectral Features (nm)																				
	1130	1187	1212	1263	1421	1427	1661	1680	1698	1717	1736	1761	1768	1906	2146	2171	2241	2266	2317	2355	
HDPE	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
LLDPE	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
MDPE	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
PVC	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
UPVC	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PS1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0
PS80	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0
PP	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
PA	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
PET	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0

addressing table. Finally, the identification results are shown.

3.1. Spectra of microplastics assembly in air and in water

To analyze the spectra of each MP type, we used hyperspectral images of individual plastics in air and in water. On each image, we perform the flat-field correction to obtain a spectral reflectance image. Next, we manually sample each MP type to obtain the representative reflectance. From VIS-NIR images, we collect the samples by averaging the values of a 5×5 pixels area from the center of each cuvette in the individual MP image. From SWIR images, the average was sampled from a 2×2 pixels area at the same spatial location. The difference in the averaged area is due to differences in resolution of the two cameras. Finally, for preview purposes, we resampled and combined the sampled reflectance of the two cameras to display one spectrum in the full wavelength range from 400 nm to 2500 nm for each plastic type. As an output, we obtain a representative reflectance spectrum for each MP type and a representative reflectance for each MP type in water.

First let us discuss the pure MP reflectance. One can observe that the reflectance spectrum in the VIS-NIR region does not exhibit any spectral features that would make different plastics easily distinguishable. Some subtle changes can be observed in the levels of the curves and the slopes of the curves. However, those are not sufficient for easy plastic identification regarding the exploitation of intrinsic spectral fingerprints of the plastic type of this study. Nevertheless, the reflectance at VIS spectral range shows some potential in the interpretation of plastic type by density and refractive index. The density of LLDPE is lowest, MDPE is between, and HDPE is the highest among these plastic types. However, all three have density lower than that of water. Hence, all these plastics float over water. If we compare in the VIS spectral range the difference of reflectance of LLDPE, MDPE and HDPE in air and in water, it is obvious that the difference is negligible in case of LLDPE but is relatively large in the case of MDPE and even larger for HDPE. At VIS, both the three plastics and water have negligible absorption of light. The difference in reflectance between the three plastics gives another measure enabling a discrimination between them in addition to the spectral features observed in the NIR. Qualitatively, for similar volume and appearance of LLDPE, MDPE and HDPE of an irregular-shaped MP, obviously the lowest density MP will show the largest cross-section projection area, and HDPE the smallest area regarding the probe light interaction with the MP. Considering the case of a population of different types of PE-based MPs floating over water surface there are places between MPs where reflection is purely from a mirror-like water surface. In case we would have exactly same populations and same particles in the same locations over a water surface with the only difference of the density of the MP material, then due to different buoyancy of MPs the total area of mirror-like water portions between neighboring MPs would be largest for HDPE and smallest for LLDPE. It yields a difference of reflectance. This is obvious from the reflectance shown in Fig. 4. In the setup presented in Fig. 2a to detect the spectrum, the idea is to collect diffuse reflection of light from the object. The ensemble of irregular MPs having different sizes (sieve size of 1 mm for LLDPE and MDPE, and 80 μm for PS) and morphologies (milling can cause surface roughness) tend to contribute to the formation of diffuse reflection, whereas mirror-like water contributes to the formation of specular reflection that is missed by the hyperspectral imagers. While the MP is deeper in water the portion of specular reflection increases from water. It yields a decrease of the reflectance at VIS spectral range while MPs are partly immersed into water. In VIS spectral range the refractive index of plastic is higher than that of the water. In the case of LLDPE-MPs, the reflectance curves in air and in water are almost overlapping. This feature suggests a similar kind of diffuse reflection, namely just if densely packed MPs floating over water would yield diffuse reflection like a plastic-air system only. While wavelength of the probe light is increasing towards SWIR the absorption of both water and plastic will contribute to the decrease of the strength of the reflectance as shown in

Fig. 4, i.e., water absorption in SWIR is higher than in VIS range of light. This case will be treated in more detail below.

Another interesting qualitative feature can be observed from the reflectance data of PS, PET, PA, and PP plastics in water. A previous study dealt with the refractive index ratio of these plastics and water (Kanyathare et al., 2020). The wavelength-dependent refractive index of plastics sheets was measured using an ellipsometer and the values for water were from literature. The magnitude of the refractive index ratio of plastic and water rules the strength of both diffuse and specular reflection from the plastic-water interface in low absorption spectral range of visible light. The refractive index ratio has a monotonic decrease with increasing wavelength, and overall, a highest value at VIS is for PS, then PET followed by PA and PP. The magnitude of the reflectance along the plateau type curves at VIS in Fig. 4 for PS, PET, PA, and PP in water follow the same order as the refractive index ratio. This refractive index concept could be an additional quantitative figure of merit to discriminate the plastic types together with spectral fingerprints in the aim of identification of different type of MPs in water, but it is a topic requiring a more detailed study.

In the following, we will focus on the IR spectral fingerprints that are due to vibrations of C—H, O—H and N—H bonds in polymer materials for the identification of plastic types. Some of such fingerprints can be detected even from plastics that are embedded in water (Peiponen et al., 2019). In the SWIR region, one can observe several valleys in the spectra that are different for different plastic types. The region between 1100 and 1300 nm, the region around 1400 nm, the region between 1600 and 1800 nm, the region between 2100 and 2250 nm and the region after 2300 nm are containing peaks and valleys that are different for the different studied MP types and hence can be used to identify and differentiate them. These valleys correspond to absorption peaks that these MP types have.

Our interest in this study is not the fluctuation of the spectral features from an MP to another but rather their change when MPs are in water, which is affecting their reflectance, as discussed above. In the SWIR region the reflectance spectral feature changes are more pronounced. First effects of water on the MPs' reflectance shares can be observed already in NIR around the first absorption peak of water at 970 nm. All MPs' reflectance in water will exhibit a valley in this spectral region. The second change can be noted around 1200 nm and the third around 1450 nm, all of which correspond to absorption peaks of water. After 1450 nm all MPs' reflectance shape flattens out and the level drops significantly. This is due to strong absorption of water in the SWIR region.

Based on these observations for this study we will focus on the SWIR region, where pure MPs have more spectral features we can exploit for identification and differentiation.

3.2. Spectral features of microplastics in water

In this section we present the result obtained by following the procedure exposed in Section 2.3 from step 1 to 4. It enables identification of different MP types by HSI from samples in water. Fig. 5 shows the spectral reflectance curves of the ten MP types in water separately after subtraction of water background and correction with 1550 nm channel.

Comparing the corrected spectra on Fig. 5 with the reflectance of MPs in water on Fig. 4, we can observe that the procedure enhances the spectral features that were suppressed by water. By observing the valleys for different MP types, we can identify differences between the group of HDPE/LLDPE/MDPE, the group of PVC/UPVC, PS, PP, PA, and PET. The group of HDPE/LLDPE/MDPE shows a 'W'-shaped pattern in the region 1730 nm to 1800 nm with minima at wavelengths 1742 nm and 1774 nm. Other MP types do not show this kind of behavior in this region. Within this group we also observe HDPE having a valley with minimum at 1136 nm while MDPE and LDPE have a valley at 1125 nm. In the region between 2300 nm and 2400 nm we can see another 'W'-shaped pattern for this group with minima at 2323 nm and 2367 nm. This pattern does not appear for any other MP type.

Fig. 5. Reflectance in the wavelength range of 920–2530 nm of the ten MPs in water after subtraction of water and correction with 1550 nm signal (denoted by the name of the plastic and index 'n'). Gray stripes mark the regions around the spectral features selected in Table 3. No smoothing was applied to the data.

PVC and UPVC both have a relatively flat spectrum after 1400 nm. We can also notice that their spectra are similar to PA in this region which makes it harder to differentiate between them. However, PVC and UPVC exhibit a small dip at 1724 nm which differentiates them from PA. At the same time, PVC, UPVC and PA show valleys with minima at 1136 nm which is same as for HDPE, PS, PP and PET. PS has a valley with minimum at 1692 nm and another one at 2177 nm which distinguishes it from any other MP types. PP has a valley in the range of 1700 nm to 1760 nm with a minimum at 1717 nm distinguishing it from any other MP types. The second valley appears in the region between 2270 nm and 2340 nm with minima at 2291 nm and 2323 nm. PA does not exhibit any valleys that are different from other MPs. Finally, PET can be distinguished by a valley with a minimum at 1667 nm and another valley at 2350 nm. From this analysis we find that removing the water background enables recovering spectral features leading to the identification and discrimination of the group of HDPE/LLDPE/MDPE, the group of PVC/UPVC, PS, PP, PA, and PET.

To ensure a more robust identification of the MPs and their types, the first derivative of the corrected reflectance spectra is used. A negative first derivative value suggests a decline at a certain wavelength of the spectral curve (suggesting a coming valley) and positive suggests an incline (a coming peak) at that wavelength. Fig. 6 shows the first derivative plots in the SWIR range of light from 1000 nm to 2500 nm of the ten MPs in water after subtraction of water reflectance and correction with 1550 nm channel. From the first derivative spectra we identified 20 wavelengths of interest at which different MPs exhibit a feature. This allows us to create a MP spectral feature addressing table (Table 3) from

which we can derive a combination of wavelengths that is unique for each MP type. Table 3a shows the values of the first derivative for each MP at selected wavelengths and Table 3b shows how that translates to a binary mask that identifies them in a spectral image.

The first derivative table allows the creation of identification rules to create a binary matrix to be applied to each pixel of each hyperspectral image leading to the identification of MPs. Every pixel of a spectral image is then run through the rule and assign value 1 if the rule is satisfied and 0 if not. The rule contains conditions for each MP type in a form of a combination of gradient values that a pixel must satisfy to be labeled as a specific MP type, else it will be labeled as background. To test the spectral feature addressing table and the labeling rule we run the method on the spectral images of single plastics from which the representative spectra were sampled. Fig. 7 shows the results of the identification.

While running this test we observed that not all wavelengths identified in Table 3 are needed for MPs identification and that we can narrow the number down to 2–4 spectral features per MP type. Some identifications of some MPs lack precision, this will be discussed in Sections 3.3 and 3.4, when addressing the case of MP mixtures. Based on the results of this test we can update the spectral feature addressing table. Table 4 shows the final table that will be used to identify MPs in mixtures.

From Table 4 we can see that to identify the HDPE/LLDPE/MDPE group it is sufficient to analyze the first derivative values at only four wavelengths, i.e., 1736 nm, 1768 nm, 2317 nm, and 2355 nm. For the PVC/UPVC group only two features are sufficient, i.e., 1717 nm and

Fig. 6. First derivative in the range of 1000–2500 nm of the ten microplastics in water after subtraction of water and baseline correction with 1550 nm channel. Dashed lines mark the spectral features identified in Table 4. The color of the bounding box around the wavelength is the same as the color of the derivative curve of a microplastic this wavelength will identify.

1736 nm. PS1/PS80 can be identified using the combination of features at 1680 nm, 2146 nm, and 2171 nm. PP can be found by 1698 nm and 2266 nm analysis, PA by observing 1130 nm, 1736 nm and 2171 nm and PET with the results at 1661 nm, 1906 nm, and 2241 nm. In the continuation we will use only these channels to identify MPs in mixtures.

3.3. Identification and location of microplastics in an MP mixture in water

To identify MPs in an MP mixture in water we run the mixture of MPs images through all the steps of the procedure using the final spectral feature addressing table (Table 4). Fig. 8 shows the results of MP identification in a mixture where each color represents a specific MP type

Fig. 7. Individual MP identification test. Top row – channel 25, 1072 nm, of the original SWIR spectral image of each MP. Bottom row - same channel overlaid with the MP identification mask (red) for each MP.

Table 4

Final identification mask for the identification of ten plastic types in water after HSI in the SWIR wavelength range. Green, from negative first derivative. Orange, from positive first derivative.

MP type	Spectral Features (nm)													
	1130	1661	1680	1698	1717	1736	1768	1906	2146	2171	2241	2266	2317	2355
HDPE						1	1						1	1
LLDPE						1	1						1	1
MDPE						1	1						1	1
PVC					1	1								
UPVC					1	1								
PS1			1						1	1				
PS80			1						1	1				
PP				1								1		
PA	1					1				1				
PET		1						1			1			

and with black, we show areas of the image that are identified as plastic, however differentiation between MP types was unsuccessful, since they are labeled as more than one class.

From Fig. 8, the proposed method allows clearly identifying and distinguishing the group HDPE/LLDPE/MDPE, the group PS1/PS80, the group UPVC/PVC, PP and PET. However, the method still faces challenges with distinguishing PA in a mixture, which is mainly due to the flatness of the PA spectrum itself. We can also note the confusion areas in the images, marked in black, where our method detects the presence of MPs but cannot distinguish between them. This could be explained by MPs being physically mixed, superimposed, or too close to each other compared to the camera resolution. Imaging conditions (illumination, shadows, reflections, noise etc.) could also distort the signal so that some spectral features cannot be resolved. Finally, we would like to point out that in this paper, we do not address in deep the question of noise and its effect on MP identification.

3.4. Complex sample of mixture of microplastics at low concentration in water

The final test of the method is done with a simulant of a realistic MP mixture in water, typically what could be found in industrial water. Fig. 9 shows the results of MP identification where each color represents a distinct MP type and with black, we show areas of the image that are identified as plastic without differentiation between MP types.

From Fig. 9, we can once again confirm the initial hypothesis we derived from analyzing the spectral features of MPs in Section 3.2. With our method we can identify and distinguish the group HDPE/LLDPE/MDPE, the group PS1/PS80, the group UPVC/PVC, PP, and PET. Our method faces challenges with distinguishing PA in a mixture at small concentration as well. The reasons for this most probably lie in the flatness of the PA spectrum itself. The absence of peaks and valleys has proven to be insufficient for a convincing identification of this MP type in a mixture. However, we can notice that the areas of confusion in these images are significantly reduced (only few pixels) than in the higher concentration mixtures. This encourages the idea that our method can successfully detect MP types at a microscale and when present in water in very small concentration. Within the limits in spatial resolution of the camera in use for the measurement, this quantitative method also allows the counting of MP particles. With the used imaging setup 12 pixels in a millimeter can be resolved with the VIS-NIR imaging system, and 2 pixels in a millimeter with the SWIR imaging system. We can also notice that some single pixels are mistakenly identified as UPVC/PVC and PP in a mix where they should not be present. This could be due to noise or operator error while performing the mixing. Deeper studies on the effects of noise will be done in the future. Finally, we can notice that the identification masks are of a very jagged shape. This is a drawback that can be attributed to the resolution of the imaging device. To be able to fully detect the true shape of the particle a higher spatial resolution is needed.

Fig. 8. Identification of MP types in an MP mixture in water. Top image – channel 25, 1072 nm, of the original SWIR spectral image of MP mixture. Bottom image - same channel overlaid with the MP identification mask. a) mixture of HDPE, LLDPE, MDPE, PS 1 and PS 80 from left to right. b) mixture of PP, UPVC, PVC, PA and PET from left to right.

4. Discussion

This paper investigates the possibility of direct hyperspectral imaging of MPs in water samples in view of integration in conventional imaging systems for in field or in line monitoring of MPs, either in industrial water or in open environment. The detection of MPs in water, and in environment in general, is currently of utmost importance for many reasons related to global matters affecting humankind, fauna, and flora, e.g., health issue, pollution, climate change, species extinction, extreme weather conditions. MPs in nature are entirely due to human activity in the past 70 years or so. The circulation of MPs in water is going in two directions. Some MPs are currently released from industry, ground, and soil pollution, and find their way to open water streams. Some MPs are generated by the degradation of bigger plastic waste already in water since many years and are coming back in the drinking and industrial water circulation (Pandey et al., 2023). These are potentially most dangerous since regulations on plastic constituents were not well established at the beginning of its usage, and these plastics may contain elements that are now forbidden. Consequently, it is extremely important to identify the MP particles in urban water networks. The robust analytical methods briefly mentioned in introduction are the most precise and reliable, however, the time-consuming pre-treatment, sorting, and preparation of the samples is not cost effective and perhaps not sufficient for screening large areas. The method proposed in this article is simple and requires basic scientific skills after its establishment. The data analysis can be implemented in machine learning/cloud based computing, or artificial intelligence algorithms for even faster image correction and precise results.

We described and demonstrated here a procedure based on the use of HSI to, at least, help for a pre-screening of water samples prior deeper analysis when necessary. We already discussed most of the results, however, during our investigation we raised several issues that we would like to discuss in this final section.

The first point is the establishment of the procedure itself. It requires

Fig. 9. Identification of MP types in realistic water sample simulant. Each cuvette contains a different mixture of five MPs. Top row – channel 25, 1072 nm, of the original SWIR spectral image of MP mixture. Bottom row - same channel overlaid with the MP identification mask. Left column: mixture of PA, HDPE, PET, PS1 and PP. Right column: mixture of PVC, UPVC, LLDPE, MDPE and PS80.

knowledge of the water matrix to enable an accurate correction or referencing of the hyperspectral images. The concentration of MPs being usually low, this should not be a problem when dealing with non-filtrated samples. In the case of filtrated samples, with higher concentration, the buffer liquid is known and can be imaged to serve as a reference.

It brings to the second issue, which is directly linked to concentration. We observed, in all cases, a gathering of the MPs in the center of the cuvette. This comes from the surface tension of the liquid in use, i.e., tap water in this study. This aggregation of the MPs leads to difficulties for identification, although the detection remains possible. To increase the visibility of different MP particles in an aggregate and in general in a water matrix higher spatial resolution of the hyperspectral imaging device is needed.

The final point deals with the cuvette used for the measurements. It does not allow MPs to completely be immersed in water despite a 7 mm water thickness. A more elaborate V-shaped cuvette allowing a flow of water and a collection of MPs in the tip of the “V” would provide more accurate results together with an imaging in depth of a water sample.

However, this would also require optical elements operating with high accuracy over a very broad wavelength range.

5. Conclusion

This article presents detection and identification of arbitrary shaped microplastics in water samples using hyperspectral imaging and an identification table. The main goal is to provide a solution for a rapid but reliable screening of samples prior robust spectroscopic analysis such as Raman and FTIR. Along the study we faced challenges in defining what cuvette type to use and had to develop our own. After removing the background and water influence on the spectra, we use an identification table to analyze the data. This identification table is set after studying microplastics with HSI and conventional spectroscopic methods. It uses spectral features of the first derivative reflectance at specific wavelengths, which eliminates the storage of the full spectral cube. It is to be noted that the method we developed for this investigation can be adapted for online measurements because our algorithm is simplified and no extensive computational resource is needed, therefore enabling almost continuous monitoring. The drawbacks of our method are mostly coming from HSI camera resolution, which is constantly improving. Current advances in AI-based analysis are also providing further promises for even faster algorithms. Finally, it is important to mention the role of the water matrix. Real water matrix found in environment can be extremely complex since water can contain other chemicals interacting and reacting with the MP and changing their spectra or particles of other kinds, e.g., biofilm, organic material, metal particles, that may hide the MP. However, the method presented in this article can be modified to account for these changes.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

A. Gebejes: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **B. Hrovat:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **D. Semenov:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **B. Kanyathare:** Writing – review & editing. **T. Itkonen:** Resources. **M. Keinänen:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **A. Koistinen:** Writing – review & editing. **K.-E. Peiponen:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Formal analysis. **M. Roussey:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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